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Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions

It decreased by 25.6% on average between 2004 and 2018

ISTAT-BES calculates the mortality rate from cancer in the age group between 20 and 64 years.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the mortality rate from cancer. The Campania region ranks first in terms of cancer mortality with a value of 9.8 units, followed by Sardinia with an amount of 9.1 and Piedmont with an amount of 8.8 units. In the middle of the table there are Lazio with a value of 8.5 units, followed by Puglia and Basilicata with an amount of 8.4 units. Umbria closes the ranking with a value of 7.9 units, followed by Valle d'Aosta with an amount of 6.9 units and Trentino-Alto Adige with an amount of 6.8 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in cancer mortality. In first place by value of the percentage change in cancer mortality between 2004 and 2018 is Abruzzo with an amount equal to -11.96% equal to an amount of -1.10 units, followed by Sicily with a value of -13.00% equal to a value of -1.30 units, and from Calabria with a value of -15.63% equal to an amount of -1.50 units. In the middle of the table there are Piedmont with an amount equal to -24.79% equal to an amount of -2.90 units, followed by Molise with a variation of -25.86% equal to an amount of -3.00 units and from Veneto with a value equal to -25.93% equal to an amount of -2.80 units. Lombardy closes the ranking with a change equal to an amount of -31.93% equal to a value of -3.80 units, followed by Trentino-Alto Adige with a change equal to an amount of -35.85% equal to an amount of -3.80 units and from Valle d'Aosta with an amount equal to -47.73% equal to an amount of -6.30 units.

Italian macro-regions. Cancer mortality decreased in all Italian macro-regions. In Northern Italy, cancer mortality decreased from an amount of 11.5 to a value of 8.2 units or equal to a variation of -3.30 units equal to a value of -28.70%. Mortality in Central Italy decreased from an amount equal to 11.2 units to a value of 8.2 units or equal to a variation of -3.00 units equal to a value of -26.79%. Mortality from cancer in Southern Italy decreased from an amount of 10.6 units to a value of 8.9 units or equal to a variation of -1.70 units equal to an amount of -16.04%. Mortality from cancer in Italy decreased from an amount of 11.2 units up to a value of 8.4 units or equal to a variation of -2.80 units equal to a value of -25.00%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm. The k-Means algorithm was used for the clustering of the Italian regions. The Silhouette coefficient was used for the optimization of the k-Means algorithm. The following clusters derive from it:

- Cluster 1: Puglia, Calabria, Marche, Abruzzo, Umbria, Trentino-Alto Adige, Basilicata, Veneto, Emilia-Romagna, Tuscany, Molise, Sicily;
- Cluster 2: Sardinia, Campania, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Piedmont, Lazio, Valle d'Aosta, Lombardy, Liguria.

However, considering the median of the clusters, it appears that the value of cancer mortality in the regions of cluster 1-C1 is equal to an amount of 8.05, while the median of mortality from cancer in

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the regions of cluster 2 is equal to 8.55. unit. Therefore, the following ordering of the clusters derives, i.e. C2> C1.

Machine Learning and Predictions. An analysis with machine learning algorithms for predicting the value of cancer mortality in the Italian regions is presented below. The algorithms were trained with 70% of the data while the remaining 30% was used for actual prediction. The algorithms were evaluated based on the ability to maximize the R-square and minimize the following statistical errors, namely: Mean Absolute Error, Mean Squared Error, Root Mean Squared Error. The following order was derived from this, that is:

- ANN-Artificial Neural Network with a payoff value of 6;
- Tree Ensemble Regression with a payoff value of 8;
- Random Forest Regression with a payoff value of 12;
- Simple Regression Tree with a payoff value of 19;
- PNN-Probabilistic Neural Network with a payoff value of 19;
- Gradient Boosted Tree with a payoff value of 20;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 29;
- Polynomial Regression with a payoff value of 31.

Through the application of the ANN-Artificial Neural Network algorithm it is possible to make the following predictions, namely:

- Piedmont with a decrease from an amount of 0.67 units up to a value of 0.54 units or equal to a value of -0.12 units equal to a value of -18.59%;
- Liguria with a decrease from an amount of 0.60 units up to a value of 0.52 units or equal to a value of -0.08 units shares at a value of -12.67%;
- Veneto with a decrease from an amount of 0.40 units up to a value of 0.28 units or equal to a variation of -0.13 units equal to an amount of -31.25%;
- Abruzzo with a decrease from an amount of 0.40 units up to a value of 0.46 units or an increase equal to an amount of 0.02 units equal to a value of 5.54%;
- Calabria with an increase from an amount of 0.43 units up to a value of 0.49 units or equal to a variation of 0.06 units equal to an amount of 14.09%;
- Sicily with a decrease from an amount of 0.63 units equal to a variation of 0.54 units equal to a variation of -0.09 units equal to a variation of -14.85%.

On average for the regions considered, the algorithm predicts a reduction in the value of cancer mortality from an amount of 0.53 units up to a value of 0.47 units or equal to a value of -0.06 units equal to an amount of -10.55%.

Conclusions. The value of cancer mortality decreased in all Italian regions between 2004 and 2018. The regions with the highest levels of cancer mortality are Campania, Sardinia and Piedmont. It is likely that the increase in cancer mortality in certain regions is due to aspects of environmental pollution due to both poor management of the territory and the impact of industrialization.

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Appendix

Mortalità per Tumore nel 2018.

**Variazione percentuale della mortalità per tumori
tra il 2004 ed il 2018**

Rank	Regione	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ -1,10	★ -11,96
2	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ -1,30	★ -13,00
3	<i>Calabria</i>	★ -1,50	★ -15,63
4	<i>Puglia</i>	★ -1,60	★ -16,00
5	<i>Campania</i>	★ -2,10	★ -17,65
6	<i>Sardegna</i>	★ -2,20	★ -19,47
7	<i>Marche</i>	★ -2,20	★ -21,57
8	<i>Liguria</i>	★ -2,70	★ -23,89
9	<i>Piemonte</i>	★ -2,90	★ -24,79
10	<i>Molise</i>	★ -3,00	★ -25,86
11	<i>Veneto</i>	★ -2,80	★ -25,93
12	<i>Lazio</i>	★ -3,10	★ -26,72
13	<i>Umbria</i>	★ -2,90	★ -26,85
14	<i>Toscana</i>	★ -3,10	★ -27,93
15	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ -3,20	★ -28,83
16	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ -3,60	★ -29,75
17	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ -3,60	★ -30,00
18	<i>Lombardia</i>	★ -3,80	★ -31,93
19	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol</i>	★ -3,80	★ -35,85
20	<i>Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste</i>	★ -6,30	★ -47,73
	Media	★ -2,8	★ -25,59

Clusterizzazione per valore della Mortalità per Tumore. C2>C1.

	R ²	mean absolute error	mean squared error	root mean squared error
ANN	0,1548744718	0,2559273003	0,1382865990	0,3718690617
PNN	-1,3319758528	0,2974137931	0,2009553772	0,4482804671
Simple Regression Tree	-0,8025814191	0,3763955343	0,1987610937	0,4458263044
Gradient Boosted Tree	-0,7423070706	0,3478292266	0,2053873832	0,4531968482
Random Forest Regression	-0,7498834701	0,2919989367	0,1671146748	0,4087966179
Tree Ensemble Regression	-0,3964077547	0,3114002478	0,1361497561	0,3689847640
Linear Regression	-3,1413156979	0,5459770115	0,3929845422	0,6268847918
Polynomial Regression	-2,2384105960	0,6666666667	0,6429980276	0,8018715780

	2018 Prediction	Var Ass	Var Per
Piemonte	0,67	0,54	-0,12
Liguria	0,60	0,52	-0,08
Veneto	0,40	0,28	-0,13
Abruzzo	0,43	0,46	0,02
Calabria	0,43	0,49	0,06
Sicilia	0,63	0,54	-0,09
Media	0,53	0,47	-0,06

	2018	Regioni	Cluster
5	6.8	Trentino-Alto A...	C1
6	8.0	Veneto	C1
8	7.9	Emilia-Romagna	C1
9	8.0	Toscana	C1
10	7.9	Umbria	C1
11	8.0	Marche	C1
13	8.1	Abruzzo	C1
14	8.6	Molise	C1
16	8.4	Puglia	C1
17	8.4	Basilicata	C1
18	8.1	Calabria	C1
19	8.7	Sicilia	C1
1	8.8	Piemonte	C2
2	6.9	Valle d'Aosta/V...	C2
3	8.6	Liguria	C2
4	8.1	Lombardia	C2
7	8.5	Friuli-Venezia G...	C2
12	8.5	Lazio	C2
15	9.8	Campania	C2
20	9.1	Sardegna	C2

